

Database and Structure Modeling of Personnel Safety Management Information System

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Abstract: This article discusses the process of modeling the database of the personnel safety management information system and its structure. In the article, the main attention in the design and creation of the database structure of the security system is paid to improving the safety of personnel. The design process outlines the risks associated with personnel performance, ways to eliminate them, and ways to integrate information necessary for monitoring safety situations into the database. The efficiency and convenience of the information system structure are also taken into account. The article describes the importance of the database used to ensure the safety of employees and related technological solutions.

Keywords: personnel safety, information system, database, structural modeling, risk management, security, algorithm, regression, normalization

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada xodimlar xavfsizligini boshqarish uchun axborot tizimining ma'lumotlar bazasini va uning strukturasi modellashtirish jarayoni yoritilgan. Maqolada xavfsizlik tizimining ma'lumotlar bazasini loyihalash va tuzilishini yaratishda asosiy e'tibor xodimlarning ishlash xavfsizligini oshirishga qaratilgan. Loyihalash jarayonida xodimlarning ish faoliyati bilan bog'liq xavf-xatarlar, ularni bartaraf etish usullari va xavfsizlik holatlarini kuzatish uchun zarur bo'lgan axborotlarni ma'lumotlar bazasiga integratsiya qilish usullari bayon etilgan. Shuningdek, axborot tizimi tuzilishining samaradorligi va foydalanuvchilarga qulayligi ko'rib chiqilgan. Maqola xodimlar xavfsizligini ta'minlash bo'yicha ishlatiladigan ma'lumotlar bazasining ahamiyatini va u bilan bog'liq texnologik yechimlarni tavsiflaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: xodimlar xavfsizligi, axborot tizimi, ma'lumotlar bazasi, struktura modellashtirish, xavf-xatar boshqaruvi, xavfsizlik, algoritim, regressiya, normalizatsiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается процесс моделирования базы данных информационной системы управления безопасностью персонала и ее структуры. В статье основное внимание при проектировании и создании структуры базы данных системы безопасности уделяется повышению безопасности работы персонала. В процессе проектирования излагаются риски, связанные с производительностью персонала, способы их устранения и способы интеграции в базу данных информации, необходимой для мониторинга ситуаций безопасности. Также учитывается эффективность и удобство структуры информационной системы. В статье описывается важность используемой базы данных для обеспечения безопасности сотрудников и связанных с ней технологических решений.

Ключевые слова: безопасность персонала, информационная система, база данных, структурное моделирование, управление рисками, безопасность, алгоритм, регрессия, нормализации.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ensuring employee safety is essential for maintaining both the efficiency and continuity of an enterprise. Establishing and monitoring workplace safety standards is a crucial tool for protecting human life and health, as well as ensuring the uninterrupted flow of production processes. Today, the application of information technology to automate safety processes is experiencing significant growth. Through information systems, it is possible to quickly identify and analyze potential risks related to employee safety, providing rapid access to relevant data [1]. Additionally, systems for monitoring safety conditions, preparing reports, and overseeing compliance are of considerable importance in enhancing employee safety.

This article examines the issues surrounding the modeling of a database and its structure for an information system designed to ensure employee safety. Properly designing the structure of the database helps improve system efficiency and creates a user-friendly interface for users [2,3]. The article proposes approaches aimed at developing a safety information system and enhancing its effectiveness.

In scientific studies on employee safety, identifying and managing risks through information technology is considered a key topic. In their research, V. Panchenko, A. Zamula, S. Kavun, and I. Mikheev [4] recommend developing information systems that enable real-time monitoring and analysis for safety systems. These systems have shown positive results in mitigating risks related to employees. Furthermore, research by Andrew Todoshchuk, Uliana Motorniuk, Tetiana Skliaruk, Ihor Oliinyk, and Tetiana Kornieieva provides a detailed analysis of methods to improve the structure of information systems for automating safety conditions [5]. Their studies highlight the crucial role of a well-structured database

in a safety system, as it is a fundamental component in automating safety processes. D.L. Nazareth and J.A. Choi emphasize the importance of focusing on the modeling process of the database when developing information systems for safety. This approach provides an opportunity for accurately and promptly identifying risks and effectively managing employee safety conditions [6].

An analysis of these sources reveals that creating and advancing a well-structured information system for ensuring employee safety remains a highly relevant topic.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Mathematical model of the database of the information system of Personnel Security Management

To develop a mathematical model for the information system database of employee safety management, it is essential to analyze the system's main components, their interconnections, and safety states. This model enables the inclusion, monitoring, and assessment of indicators that help measure and control employee safety levels. The following fundamental elements and their relationships are considered for constructing this model.

For each employee, we define a risk assessment score as the sum of various safety indicators.

$$\begin{cases} R(x_1) = \sum_{k=1}^m w_k \cdot s_k(x_1, T) \\ R(x_2) = \sum_{k=1}^m w_k \cdot s_k(x_2, T) \\ \vdots \\ R(x_i) = \sum_{k=1}^m w_k \cdot s_k(x_i, T) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where w_k — represents the weight assigned to each safety indicator s_k , x — is the set of employees $x = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i\}$, where x_i denotes the average or aggregated value of the s_k indicator for employee x_i over the time interval T , T — is the time interval for monitoring safety parameters, S — is the set of safety state indicators $s = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_k\}$, m — is the total number of safety parameters.

The risk assessment index $ESI_i(t)$ at time t for employee i , which combines all safety parameters [7] to determine the overall level of risk, is calculated using formula (2)

$$ESI_i(t) = \sum_{j=1}^m w_j \cdot P_{ij}(t_j) \quad (2)$$

where w_j — is the importance or weighting factor of each security parameter, and this indicator shows the level of risk in percent. The security indicators for each employee in the time interval are defined as $P_{i,j}(t)$, where $P_{i,j}(t)$ — is the value of the i - th employee to the j - security parameter. These values are normalized between 0 and 1, allowing to evaluate the security level as a percentage, t_j — is a time interval (day, week or month).

Formula 3 is presented in the form of a matrix to conveniently display the safety parameters and indicators of all employees in the system. With this matrix, security situations are analyzed and the security situation of each employee is evaluated.

$$M(t) = \begin{bmatrix} P_{1,1}(t) & P_{1,2}(t) & \dots & P_{1,m}(t) \\ P_{2,1}(t) & P_{2,2}(t) & \dots & P_{2,m}(t) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ P_{n,1}(t) & P_{n,2}(t) & \dots & P_{n,m}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

If the $ESI_i(t)$ forecast indicates that safety standards are not met, automated warning or safety action systems are triggered. Simple regression or artificial intelligence algorithms, Bayesian networks or time series models can be used for analysis [8].

3. RESULTS

In Figure 1 below, we used simple linear regression to analyze employee safety performance over time $ESI_i(t)$.

Fig. 1. Linear regression graph of $ESI_i(t)$ time dependence of employee safety indicators.

Figure 1 depicts the Employee Safety Index (ESI) over time, showing both actual and forecasted values. In this graph, the blue dots represent the measured actual values of the Employee Safety Index, $ESI_i(t)$. It is evident from the graph that

the *ESI* values fluctuate, with certain days showing a decrease in the index (e.g., on day 3) while other days show an increase.

The red line indicates the forecasted *ESI* values for future days. A linear regression model was employed for this forecast, which allows us to see how the *ESI* index is expected to evolve based on the measured values. The forecast suggests that the projected values will rise above the minimum safety level in the future.

The green line represents the minimum safety index threshold, $ESI_{min} = 0.8$, which defines the minimum acceptable safety standard, meaning that *ESI* values should not fall below this line. Although the actual *ESI* values initially (between days 1 and 5) were below the minimum safety level, recent measurements and the forecast indicate that the values are expected to meet or exceed this minimum requirement moving forward. The algorithm of the indicator of the safety index of the employee is given in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Algorithm for evaluation of safety parameters of employees

The Data Collection Module in the structure of the personnel safety management information system collects the necessary data for safety monitoring. It collects data using a variety of sensors and equipment to record employee safety performance, inspection results, and risk factors. Database serves to store and manage all security information collected. The database includes all information

such as personnel, safety indicators, time interval, risk factors and provides quick access. Data Processing and Analysis Module analyzes the collected data and evaluates security indicators. This module processes data to generate risk analysis and statistical reports. Management and Monitoring Module serves to control the security status of employees. This module allows you to implement and monitor security policies, monitor and analyze dangerous situations. The User Interface makes it easy to monitor security information, view reports, and manage security status. The Decision-making Module helps in the decision-making process regarding safety issues and risk factors [9]. Based on the analysis, the level of risk, security measures and other recommendations, the structure of the information system is given in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. The structure of the information system of personnel safety management.

4. DISCUSSIONS

The discussion section analyzes the advantages, limitations, and practical applications of the information system developed to ensure employee safety. This system provides new capabilities for real-time monitoring of employee safety, swiftly identifying and preventing potential hazards. During the database modeling process, the structured and comprehensive collection of all safety-related information enhances the system's efficiency. Furthermore, the information system facilitates rapid decision-making for necessary actions in response to risks that may arise in employees' work activities. In this process, the database's composition and proper structure play a crucial role.

However, certain limitations are observed when implementing the information system. Beyond the technical requirements of the software, the competence of employees in handling information technologies is essential. Additionally, financial resources and the provision of necessary technological equipment for accurately assessing safety conditions are required for system implementation. Applying this

system in practice introduces the opportunity to elevate safety measures to a new qualitative level, ensuring employee protection. Moreover, analyzing the database information and automating safety-related processes aids in more efficient management of employee activities.

Overall, the safety information system can significantly impact risk reduction within enterprises and facilitate effective management of safety measures. Nonetheless, challenges related to its implementation and practical application exist, requiring further research to overcome them.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This article analyzes the modeling of the database and structure of an information system aimed at ensuring employee safety. It examines ways to optimize the database and system architecture to enhance the efficiency of the safety system. The primary purpose of the information system is to monitor the safety status of employees, rapidly identify and mitigate risks. Additionally, by designing the database correctly, the system can effectively collect and manage critical safety-related information [10,11].

The mathematical models and safety indices discussed in the article play a crucial role in assessing risk levels and enabling real-time monitoring. When the system detects conditions that do not meet safety standards, an alert mechanism is activated, prompting appropriate actions. The article highlights the practical significance of the system, exploring methods to improve its effectiveness while addressing the limitations and requirements involved in its implementation. It emphasizes the necessity of having skilled personnel who can work with data technologies and the provision of technical equipment to ensure the system operates efficiently. In conclusion, this information system enables a high level of effectiveness in ensuring employee safety. It serves to reduce risks and allows for swift, precise management of safety measures. However, further research is required to address implementation challenges.

6. REFERENCES

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